

THE ROLE OF GAME TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. *Currently, special attention is being paid to the development of creative activity and interests of pupils at schools in our country. Various competitions, Olympic Games are being held constantly. This shows that the principle of the learner's activity in the learning process has been and remains one of the basic rules in didactics. This article deals with the role of game technology in teaching English at schools focused on increasing the interests of school pupils.*

Keywords: *games, game technology, creative activity, pupils, school.*

РОЛЬ ИГРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В настоящее время развитию творческой активности и интересов учащихся в школах нашей страны уделяется особое внимание. Постоянно проводятся различные соревнования, Олимпийские игры. Это показывает, что принцип активности учащегося в процессе обучения был и остается одним из основных правил дидактики. В данной статье рассматривается роль игровых технологий в преподавании английского языка в школах, ориентированных на повышение интересов школьников.*

Ключевые слова: *игры, игровая технология, творческая деятельность, учащиеся, школа.*

One of the interactive technologies in education is gaming technology. I use game technology in English classes focused on making the learning process interesting, to create a cheerful working mood of pupils and to overcome difficulties in mastering the learning material. The game will help you solve these problems and gives good results, increases pupils' interests in the lesson and, most importantly, allows them to master speech skills in the process of a natural situation and to communicate during playing.

Language learning is hard work. Effort is required at every moment and must be maintained over a long period of time. Games help and encourage many learners to sustain their interest and work. Games also help the teacher to create contexts in which the language is useful and meaningful. The learners want to take part and in order to do so must understand what others are saying or have written, and they must speak or write in order to express their own point of view or give information.

The need for meaningfulness in language learning has been accepted for some years. A useful interpretation of meaningfulness is that the learners respond to the content in a definite way. If they are amused, angered, intrigued or surprised the content is clearly meaningful to them. Thus the meaning of the language they listen to, read, speak and write will be more vividly experienced and, therefore, better remembered. If it is accepted that games can provide intense and meaningful practice of language, then they must be regarded as central to a teacher's repertoire. They are thus not for use solely on wet days and at the end of term!

The essence of didactic play is that pupils solve mental problems put forward by him in the form of entertaining games, find their own solutions, and to overcome certain difficulties. The learner perceives the mental task as a practical, playful task; this increases his mental activity.

In didactic play, a learner's emotional development is inextricably linked to his or her logical thinking and ability to express his or her thoughts in words. To solve the game problem it is necessary to compare the signs of objects, identify similarities and differences, generalize, and draw conclusions. Thus, the ability to judge, to draw conclusions, to apply their knowledge in different situations develops. This will be possible if pupils have a clear idea of the things and events that make up the content of the game.

Game functions

- educational games (memory, attention development, information retrieval, general education skills development, foreign language development)

- communicative games (creating an environment of communication in a foreign language, uniting the student body, establishing new emotional and communicative connections based on interaction in a foreign language)

- psychological (formation of skills to prepare their physiological state for more effective activities, as well as the reconstruction of the psyche to absorb large amounts of information).

Interactive games (alleviation of emotional stress caused by stress on the nervous system with intensive learning of a foreign language)

Developmental games (harmonious development of personal qualities to activate a person's backup ability)

To understand the meaning of didactic games, the following requirements are set.

➤ Every didactic game should provide exercises that are useful for pupils's mental development and their reading.

➤ An interesting task is required in a didactic game, the solution of which requires mental strength to overcome some difficulties.

Currently, Methodists have developed many role-playing games and options for conducting them in order to increase the interest in learning a foreign language and to improve the process of teaching a foreign language. Games are divided into the following categories.

1. Lexical games;
2. Grammar games;
3. Phonetic games;
4. Spelling games;
5. Creative games.

The role of the game in the lesson and the time allotted for the game depends on a number of factors: the readiness of the pupils, the material studied the specific objectives of the lesson and conditions and so on. For example, if the game is used as a training exercise for the initial correction of the material, then the lesson may take 15-20 minutes. In the future, the same game can be played for 3-5 minutes and will serve as a repetition of material already passed, as well as a release in class. The game stimulates pupils' interests and activity, takes into account their individual abilities, gives pupils the opportunity to prove themselves in activities that are interesting to them, and contributes to faster and longer memorization.

The game can and should be included in the process of teaching a foreign language from the first lessons. For example, when learning to count, you can use a "Prospects of Development o variety of "counters" that you can not only memorize, but also use to distribute roles in the next

open game that can be used as an exercise, so that young pupils lose the accumulated fatigue during class.

When working with elementary school age pupils, you can use visual aids both to introduce and correct new lexical material and to introduce and teach some grammatical structures. In this type of game, we engage in one or two speech styles that are repeated several times. Therefore, from the point of view of organizing oral material, such a game is nothing more than a verbal exercise, but we turn the usual verbal exercise into a game and avoid the boredom and distraction that are inevitable during memorization, emotional we create a conducive environment and increase interest in learning a foreign language.

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